

Oslo, 22 August, 2024

Dear Dr Olwenn Martin,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of the manuscript “[A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to *in vitro* toxicology studies](#)”. We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback and are grateful for the comments and suggestions for improvement of our manuscript.

We have comprehensively revised our manuscript in response to Reviewer 2's request for considerably more information and descriptions. Our overall strategy in responding was to simplify and restructure the whole manuscript (i.e. we realise they ask for more details, but in fact we think the details were there but not clearly communicated enough, therefore we have attempted to simplify, and in some places shorten our manuscript). Hopefully this has made the manuscript easier to read and understand.

We have also responded to each comment individually, and the suggested revisions are shown in the table below. The table contain an overview of our point-by-point response to all comments and the revisions provided.

We look forward to hearing from you regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

Gunn E. Vist

Responses to reviewer comments

TEBT-2024-0009 | A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to in vitro toxicology studies

Comment-by-comment responses

Ref.	Reviewer comment	Response
Comments from editorial review		
1	Declaration of interests of the majority of co-authors are informative. There are nonetheless a few individual declarations where either some items have been checked under financial or non-financial interests but no detail provided, or declarations which are only signed but the previous sections have not been completed. As indicated by the notes accompanying the form, interests do not necessarily constitute a conflict of interest and ‘it is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project’.	The declarations of interest for the co-authors were completed according to the guidance in the “Notes”-section in the form. The variations in the level of information are the result of different interpretation of what the level of detail should be. To make the level of information more similar, more detailed guidance is needed to reduce the possibility for different interpretation. We therefore hope that you can accept the variation in informativeness of these declarations.
2	We gratefully acknowledge the code to generate figure in ‘Supplemental Material 6_Item Bank.pdf’. The software used (in this instance R) is not mentioned nor cited in the manuscript or in the supplemental material file.	This is now included in the result section of the revised text as follows: “We used the Obscure Reference Generator (Version 2.1; Esolang, 2014), to generate Figure 2, the code for generating the figure is available in Supplemental Material 6.”
3	Please rename the Supplemental Material files such that file name give some information contained in the file.	The supplemental material files have been renamed to give some information about the content in the file.
4	The authors have published two protocols related to this project where the context and rationale for the development of INVITES-IN are detailed. Nonetheless, this manuscript, as a stand-alone article, should present a robust rationale for conducting the research without readers needing to refer to previously published protocols. Similarly, the justification of using an item bank approach by simply referring to the PRISMA reporting item checklist approach is too succinct. This should be briefly developed.	Thank you for this comment. We agree that this manuscript should function as a stand-alone publication and have made comprehensive revisions accordingly. Rather than copy-paste text from the protocol, we have taken the opportunity to improve how we communicate our approach, and to address many of the comments from the reviewers below. This includes, for this specific comment, completely rewriting the introduction to better position the work in its context. We have also added text to the methods section explaining our reasons for using an item bank approach and how we have

		implemented this methodology. This allows us to respond to other reviewer comments below.
Comments from peer-review		
1	<p>Editor’s summary: This manuscript reports the results of the first step of the development of a risk-of-bias tool (INVITES-IN) for in vitro (cell cultures) studies, the protocol for which has been previously published here. This involved the creation of an “item bank”, a database of study assessment concepts that may be relevant to evaluating the internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies. These were derived from seven literature sources and the transcribed discussions of three focus groups. Assessment criteria plausibly relating to internal validity were disaggregated, normalised and then mapped onto a set of bias domains. The resulting item bank contains 405 items that may be important for evaluating the internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies.</p>	
“Overall impressions”		
2	<p>The assessment of the two reviewers differed widely between that of the reviewer who had previously reviewed the protocol for this study and the reviewer who had not. This suggests that information critical for the reader to understand the rationale for and significance of the work presented in the published protocol is not sufficient relayed in the manuscript. It ought to be feasible for authors to provide clarifications about rationale, objective and methods for the overall project and this specific step, as well as justification and indication of the utility of the item bank for the wider scientific community. The authors should carefully consider whether a sound justification can be provided for some of the analytical choices or whether re-analysis would be desirable.</p>	<p>We thank the reviewers for their helpful comments and agree that we could make our rationale, objectives, and methods clearer. We have made comprehensive revisions to the manuscript accordingly.</p> <p>Because our methodology is fundamentally subjective, we have focused on making clearer our approach, its strengths and limitations (e.g. section 4.1), and acknowledging how other research teams could come to different decisions than we did. Nonetheless, because we think our approach is fit for purpose, we have not reanalysed our data.</p>
3	<p>1. Thank you for the extensive and worthwhile efforts on this project, I'm extremely impressed by the scope and level of detail, and I am very much looking forward to reviewing the next phase. Also, I still prefer to consider sensitivity...but then, I'm biased :)</p>	<p>Thank you for the kind words. We can reassure the reviewer that concepts of sensitivity are still being considered, it is just that the way the concept is classified and organised is different. One could relatively easily take the item bank and methodically classify all the</p>

		<p>sensitivity-related items (some of which may not be in the tools that explicitly use this concept) if that were considered desirable. The caveat would be any criteria that were excluded for relating to imprecision, but these are still captured in the supplemental materials.</p>
4	<p>2. This paper describes the creation of an item bank to support the development of a critical appraisal tool for in vitro studies (INVITES-IN). The work is part of a larger project that includes developing and testing the INVITES-IN tool. I found this manuscript difficult to understand, as there are several substantive pieces of information missing. The manuscript also appears, unless I have misunderstood it, to end with an incomplete item bank that is not clearly signposted to the reader and has no guidance or instructions on how it should be interpreted or used.</p>	<p>We agree that we could more clearly communicate the rationale and methods for our manuscript. We have therefore rewritten the introduction section and also the introduction to the method section, and hope this made it easier to understand the manuscript.</p> <p>We agree that more information about the item bank, a guidance on the use of the item bank, is needed. We have therefore revised the results section, included a section specifically about how to use the item bank (4.4), added and included text about the structure of the item bank file that is replicated in the item bank itself.</p> <p>A new sheet is included in supplemental materials 5 with information about each sheet in this excel file, and how the item bank may be useful to other researchers:</p> <p>“Sheet 0 “Information”. The information sheet that provides guidance on the contents of the item bank file.</p> <p>Sheet 1 “Item Bank”. The item bank, consisting of the reference numbers, unique items (n=405), and the bias domains under which each item has been categorized. Each item has a unique reference number to facilitate identification and tracking through the analysis process.</p> <p>Sheet 2 “Items by Source”. The item bank, including the source and original criterion or discussion point from which each item was derived. Because some items appear in multiple sources, the total</p>

		<p>number of records in this sheet (n=497) is higher than the total number of items (n=405).</p> <p>Sheet 3 “Abstracted Criteria”. The full list of criteria and discussion points abstracted from the literature sources and focus group discussions, that were interpreted into the items.</p> <p>Sheet 4 “Included Criteria”. The criteria and discussion points containing concepts that ended up being interpreted into items and included in the item bank. This sheet shows how the criteria and discussion points were interpreted into items by the investigators.</p> <p>Sheet 5 “Excluded Criteria”. The criteria and discussion points that were not interpreted into items in the item bank.</p> <p>Sheet 6 “Lookups”. The source for the drop-down lists of bias items, designed to reduce data input errors when creating the item bank.</p> <p>Sheet 1 and 2 have been set up with filters to assist with exploring the item bank, allowing e.g. only items associated with analysis bias to be displayed (sheet 1), or only items associated with a specific source (sheet 2). The sheets are locked but not password protected to prevent accidental editing. To filter the data in the sheets, the user should right-click the tab for the sheet they are interested in filtering and select “Pause Protection”.</p>
5	<p>3. The manuscript feels esoteric in places and difficult to follow, as bias items are referred to as numeric codes that readers will have no familiarity with. Are these codes intended to cross-link to supplementary material 5? The manuscript also relies on unnecessary acronyms in places which impedes readability. I found the Discussion section very difficult to understand, lacking structure and with no clear “take-home” messages that stand out.</p>	<p>We agree that the submitted manuscript could be difficult to follow. We have addressed all these issues with comprehensive revisions throughout.</p>
<p>“Are the introduction, rationale, and hypotheses the same as in the accepted protocol?”</p>		

6	<p>Several aspects of the rationale for the overall project, this specific step of the project and for the selection of methods for this step are not evident for a reader who has not read the published protocol. Authors should relay sufficient information about the overall project, its scope, definitions or references to selected existing definitions for important concepts (e.g. bias domain) and how this specific step fits in the overall project for the manuscript to make sense as a stand-alone piece.</p>	<p>We agree that the rationale for the overall project needs clarification. We have therefore rewritten the introduction section to make this clearer. The revised introduction includes the rationale for performing this study, definitions of all main terms (e.g. internal validity, bias, bias items, and bias domains), more detailed information about INVITES-IN (e.g. the delimitation to eukaryotic cell culture studies), an elaboration of the description of the whole process for the creation of INVITES-IN, and an elaborated description of the objective of this study.</p>
7	<p>4. The paper is about the critical appraisal of in vitro studies but there is no description of the critical appraisal tools that already exist for in vitro studies and what their strengths and limitations are. So, it's not very clear to readers why new tools are needed and what specific limitations of the existing tools the work addresses.</p>	<p>We agree that it should be clarified why new tools are needed and the specific limitations of the existing tools. The following have been included in the introduction:</p> <p>“While many tools have been created for assessing validity of in vitro studies, to date there is no consensus as to which, if any, of these tools ought to be used for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021, Barbosa et al., 2023). To address this issue, we are conducting the INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity) project.”</p>
8	<p>5. It would be helpful if the paper could explain the rationale for the item bank approach and why this was selected as the method to support the development of the critical appraisal tool, given that many critical appraisal tools (e.g. those of Cochrane) have not been developed using this approach.</p>	<p>We agree that the rationale for the item bank approach and why this was selected as the method to support the development of the critical appraisal tool should be described. The following is included in the revised methods section:</p> <p>” In their proposed framework for developing quality assessment tools, Whiting and colleagues recommend an “item generation” step be part of tool development methodology (Whiting et al., 2017). However, what constitutes best practice in item generation is not, as far as we are aware, a settled matter. Our item bank development methodology follows Whaley et al. 2024 and consists of two main stages, summarised below then described more fully in the subsequent sections of this manuscript. The full details of the methodology are in our preregistered study protocol (Svensen et al., 2023).”</p>

9	<p>6. The scope of the work is not fully clear. The protocol for this research states that the work is limited to the subset of in vitro studies that involved cell cultures. The current manuscript does not mention this. Is the item bank specific to certain types of in vitro study or can it be generalised to any in vitro study?</p>	<p>We agree that the scope needs to be clarified. The following is now included in the introduction:</p> <p>“While many tools have been created for assessing validity of in vitro studies, to date there is no consensus as to which, if any, of these tools ought to be used for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021, Barbosa et al., 2023). To address this issue, we are conducting the INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity) project. The objective of INVITES-IN is to select, modify, or develop an appraisal tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies, with an initial focus on eukaryotic cell culture studies.”</p> <p>“It should be noted that while INVITES-IN is ultimately aimed at creating a tool for assessing risk of bias in studies of eukaryotic cell culture systems, the item bank includes issues for in vitro studies of any design.”</p>
10	<p>7. Lines 88-89: Perhaps it would be helpful to explain around here why INVITES-IN is necessary, as this is not explained in the manuscript. We don’t need item banks for randomised controlled trials (do we?), so why do we need them for in vitro ecotox studies?</p>	<p>We agree that it should be explained why INVITES-IN is necessary. This is included in the revised introduction:</p> <p>“Many tools have been created for assessing validity of in vitro studies, however, there is a priori lack of consensus on developing a tool with the application of rigorous methods.”</p> <p>“In a systematic review of quality assessment tools for in vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021), the conclusion was that none of the existing tools cover all critical aspects for systematic review of in vitro studies.”</p> <p>Item banks are comprehensive data sets that are valuable to ensure that the development of a tool is sufficiently grounded. As we have included in the introduction, an item bank was part of the method for updating of the PRISMA reporting checklist for systematic reviews in 2020 by Page et al. (2020). We believe that item banks are useful for</p>

		grounding and more formal development of validity assessment tools for all types of study designs.
11	8. Line 115 What are “domain experts”?	This is clarified in line 150-151: “...experts with extensive experience with in vitro studies (called “domain experts”)...”
12	9. Lines 137-150: The focus here appears illogical. There is little discussion of tools for assessing in vitro studies, yet extensive “justification” of why tools for other study designs (non in vitro) are supposedly relevant. There is no explanation of what is wrong with existing in vitro tools, so readers may struggle to understand why this work is necessary. Furthermore, the protocol states that the focus of interest is specifically on cell culture studies, not all in vitro studies, but this is not mentioned in the manuscript and has implications for the scope and generalisability of the item bank. Even the name of the “INVITES-IN” tool feels like it might not be appropriate because the tool – as far as I understand it from what the protocol says – is more specifically for assessing cell culture studies?	<p>Thank you for pointing out this. We have done the following revision of the text to clarify this:</p> <p>“While many tools have been created for assessing validity of in vitro studies, to date there is no consensus as to which, if any, of these tools ought to be used for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021, Barbosa et al., 2023). To address this issue, we are conducting the INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity) project. The objective of INVITES-IN is to select, modify, or develop an appraisal tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies, with an initial focus on eukaryotic cell culture studies.”</p> <p>“The objective of this study is to create a comprehensive database of issues relating to the design, conduct, or reporting of <i>in vitro</i> studies that may introduce bias into their results or findings. Following Page et al. (2020) and Whiting et al. (2017), we call such a database an “item bank”.”</p> <p>“It should be noted that while INVITES-IN is ultimately aimed at creating a tool for assessing risk of bias in studies of eukaryotic cell culture systems, the item bank includes issues for in vitro studies of any design.”</p> <p>We hope that this clarifies that it is the user test that will be limited to eukaryotic cell culture studies. This delimitation is necessary to be able to sufficiently power the user test study. However, the item bank contains bias items of importance for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies and it is not restricted to cell culture studies, the next</p>

		<p>study which will be performed to identify bias items of importance for assessing the internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> studies will not be restricted to cell culture studies, and neither will the design of the tool itself. We aim to identify all items of importance for the assessment of internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> studies and to cover these by INVITES-IN. However, the user testing will only include cell culture studies.</p>
13	<p>10. Since the objective is to develop a tool for assessing systematic error, I assume the item bank should be grounded in causality theory, but it is not clear how the information sources used for the developing the item bank achieve this (the systematic review is not described at all). One of the peer review comments on an earlier version of the study protocol was that “the manuscript would benefit from developing discussions about current approaches to RoB tool development, consensus around best approach and the strength and limitations of the approach adopted”. I agree with this point and believe it would be helpful.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. The item bank is descriptive of what people have said may introduce systematic error into a study, it is not a theory-driven selection of sources of systematic error where some of the proposed issues are being eliminated – this comes later.</p> <p>It is not clear to us why an item bank would need to be grounded in causal theory. To our knowledge, no internal validity appraisal tool is, and we are anyway only describing what tools that are concerned with internal validity have posited as features of the design, conduct, or reporting of a study that could introduce bias.</p>
14	<p>11. Line 393: What is “domain coverage”? What is a “domain”? None of this has been explained.</p>	<p>We agree that this is unclear, and have revised the text as follows: “The focus group discussions added a large number of items to analysis, detection, performance, and selection bias, with the practical experience of the participants able to add many considerations to bias domains of which the literature only had partial coverage. Examples of where the focus group discussions contributed items to domains that would otherwise have been almost empty are conflicted interest and choice-of-question bias.</p> <p>It is important to note that the first focus group contributed 74 new discussion items, the second 30, and the third group 28. The fact that a large proportion of new items were still being discovered in the third focus group discussion suggests that there are more items yet to be discovered. Therefore, coverage of all critical aspects for the assessment of internal validity in <i>in vitro</i> studies, even in our item bank, remains incomplete and additional focus groups would still be of high value.”</p>

15	<p>12. Lines 401-402: The fact that the study was just a discovery exercise hasn't been clearly communicated and should preferably be clarified at the start of the manuscript.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out this. We agree and have included this early in the methods (lines 117-120):</p> <p>“Our item bank development methodology follows Whaley et al. 2024 and consists of two main stages, summarised below then described more fully in the subsequent sections of this manuscript. The full details of the methodology are in our preregistered study protocol (Svendson et al., 2023).</p> <p>Stage 1. Issue discovery</p> <p>The objective of this stage is to identify a comprehensive set of issues relating to the design, conduct, or reporting of <i>in vitro</i> studies that may introduce bias into their results or findings.”</p>
16	<p>13. Section 2.3.3 of the protocol states “Study 2 will result in a list of bias domains and items (i) for which there were agreement that the domain or item is of importance when evaluating risk of bias of in vitro studies, (ii) for which there was agreement that the domain or item is not of importance when evaluating risk of bias of in vitro studies and (iii) where agreement was not reached for either inclusion or exclusion in the two rounds of Delphi or in the guided discussion. For the items where agreement was not reached, arguments for considering a given item as higher or lower importance will be included.” However, I could not see this information presented in this structured and transparent way in Supplementary material 5 or anywhere else in the manuscript documents.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment, we have clarified how the papers we are publishing map onto the studies described in the protocol.</p> <p>“The creation of INVITES-IN consists of four methodological stages, that we refer to as “studies”:</p> <p>Study 1. Creating a comprehensive database of issues that may affect the internal validity of in vitro studies of any design.</p> <p>Study 2. Prioritising issues from the database according to their relevance to the assessment of internal validity of eukaryotic cell culture systems.</p> <p>Study 3. Creating a beta version of an appraisal tool based on analysis of the prioritised issues identified in stage 2.</p> <p>Study 4. Creating a final release version of the tool, based on user-testing of the beta version.</p> <p>Due to the complexity of the INVITES-IN project, we are publishing our methods and results in three manuscripts. The present manuscript describes the methods and results for Study 1. A second manuscript will describe Study 2. The third manuscript will describe Studies 3 and 4. The planned methods for all four INVITES-IN studies, the creation</p>

		and user testing of INVITES-IN are described in two protocols (Mathisen et al., 2023; Svendsen et al., 2023).”
“Were the collected data able to test the stated hypotheses by satisfying the approved outcome-neutral conditions?”		
19	The peer-review process gave rise to detailed questions about data and their analysis, most of which can be addressed by offering some clarification of the accepted methods. Others are concerned with the interpretation and classification decisions, e.g. about bias domains or the normalisation logic. Where authors can offer sound justification for their decisions, these may also be addressed through clarification. Authors may also decide to amend some of their analyses in view of the comments provided.	<p>Thank you for this information. We have tried to clarify the methodology used, and to justify our decisions in the revised manuscript.</p> <p>We understand that the interpretation and classification decisions, e.g. about bias domains or the normalisation logic, may be done in different ways. We therefore consider that transparency of the process is critical, to make it possible for other researchers to know exactly what we have done, and to either agree with our method or to do their own interpretations and classifications if they disagree with our decisions. Therefore, as there is no absolute correct answer, but rather different ways for interpretation, we have not amended our analyses. Instead, we consider that the current item bank is fit for purpose as being the starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN. In addition, throughout the process of creating INVITES-IN, which is a stepwise process where the preparation of the item bank is the first step, the data set will be refined.</p>
20	14. The work reported relies heavily on assigning information to “bias domains”. However, the meaning of “bias domain” is not explained in the protocol or manuscript. So, it is difficult to follow the logic of the classifications employed and the decisions around which domain an item should relate to. What are the properties of a “bias domain”?	<p>Bias domain is explained in the Glossary and Table 2 lists the bias domains with definitions.</p> <p>We agree that this could be explained more, and the following is in the methods section:</p> <p>“Stage 2. Issue analysis</p> <p>The objective of this stage is to derive linguistically minimalist expressions of the study assessment concepts identified in the stage 1 (i.e. create the database of “items”) and organising these according to bias themes.</p> <p>We chose this approach because the way that bias issues are presented in appraisal tools and focus group discussions is heterogeneous and complex. This can make it challenging to discern precisely what issue is being addressed by a criterion in a tool or a</p>

		<p>point of expert discussion, and to compare tool criteria or discussion points to determine if they are in fact about the same issue. We therefore disaggregated complex appraisal criteria into their component issues and sought to eliminate irrelevant linguistic differences in how appraisal criteria are expressed in different tools and contexts (a process we refer to as “normalisation”). We also organised items into bias domains to help structure the database and make it easier to use in later stages of the INVITES-IN project.”</p>
21	<p>15. The “normalisation” process is a central part of how the item bank is created. However, I cannot follow the logic of this, because the “normalised” items appear less informative than the information that they have been extracted from. As explained in my specific comments below, this process seems to have resulted in “items” that are neither consistent nor intuitive to interpret. Perhaps I am misunderstanding the item bank and how it’s supposed to be used?</p>	<p>Thank you, we have added explanations and clarifications.</p> <p>Please see the above response to point 14.</p> <p>Please see discussion 4.1. Normalisation and exclusion decisions</p>
22	<p>16. Abstract: Lines 69-73: The total number of items in the item bank (405) is 20 fewer than the total number of items identified from the SR, focus groups and tools. Is this discrepancy due to duplicates, or something else?</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. This discrepancy is due to duplicates. Since the deduplication process is not described in the method-part of the abstract we deleted these numbers from the abstract and have revised the result-part of the abstract as follows:</p> <p>“Results: The item bank contains 405 items of potential relevance for evaluating the internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> toxicology studies.”</p>
23	<p>17. Lines 145-147: I found this paragraph confusing. The statement “The INVITES-IN item bank includes tools not designed specifically for the in vitro context ...” doesn’t correspond to the item bank, which includes items, not tools. Also, there is no explanation of whether any existing in vitro assessment tools could have been consulted.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out this need for clarification. We have revised the text to make it clear that existing validity assessment tools for in vitro studies, human studies and animal experimental studies were used as sources in the item abstraction. The text has been revised as follows:</p> <p>“Items were abstracted from the literature sources as listed in the protocol (Svendsen et al., 2023) with one additional tool (ROBINS-E). The literature sources included tools for assessment of in vitro studies, human studies, and animal experimental studies.”</p> <p>“We included assessment tools for non <i>in vitro</i> studies based on our experience that assessment concepts are quite generalizable for different types of study, and therefore that newer risk of bias tools</p>

		<p>even for epidemiological research may include concepts that could be applicable to <i>in vitro</i> studies. This way we aimed to capture emerging developments in risk of bias assessment methods and criteria that could potentially be applicable to <i>in vitro</i> study designs but may not yet have been incorporated into tools within the <i>in vitro</i> toxicology literature.”</p>
24	<p>18. Table 1: It is unclear whether all relevant tools for assessing <i>in vitro</i> studies have been included here. Are there any <i>in vitro</i> tools missing and if so why?</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out that this is unclear. The following revision of the text has been done to clarify this: “Items were abstracted from the literature sources as listed in the protocol (Svendsen et al., 2023) with one additional tool (ROBINS-E). The literature sources included a selection of published and widely used validity assessment tools, and an existing item bank covering study appraisal concepts included in 67 <i>in vitro</i> appraisal tools (Whaley et al., 2023). The literature sources included tools for assessment of <i>in vitro</i> studies, human studies, and animal experimental studies. We included assessment tools for non <i>in vitro</i> studies based on our experience that assessment concepts are quite generalizable for different types of study, and therefore that newer risk of bias tools even for epidemiological research may include concepts that could be applicable to <i>in vitro</i> studies. This way we aimed to capture emerging developments in risk of bias assessment methods and criteria that could potentially be applicable to <i>in vitro</i> study designs but may not yet have been incorporated into tools within the <i>in vitro</i> toxicology literature.”</p>
25	<p>19. Figure 1: I am not sure that the interpretation of Cooper 2016 illustrated in this Figure should be detection bias. Detection bias refers to systematic error arising from how results are measured (as indicated in Table 2). But, in this example there is a systematic deviation from the intended exposure, which is not related to measurement.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment, giving us an opportunity to explain our interpretation. We consider our interpretation to be in line with the comment for application from SEVCO: “Detection of the value of the variable comprises three processes involved in the determination of the recorded values for the variable: ascertainment (providing the opportunity for assessment), assessment (measurement and/or classification), and documentation (recording of data values for analysis).”. In our interpretation, an error in the intended exposure is</p>

		part of the process of ascertainment, resulting in an under- or over-estimate of the result.
26	20. Figure 1: I suppose “analysis bias” is okay as a descriptor here; however, I am more used to calling this “attrition bias” or “bias due to missing data” and I note that the Cochrane tools now class this as a type of selection bias.	Thank you for this comment. We interpret imputation as handling of absence of data; imputation is insertion of data and therefore a part of the analytic process applied to the data.
27	21. Line 180: At this point in the manuscript it becomes important that we are clear about what “bias domains” means. Are “domains” mutually exclusive categories of independent bias types that prevent sources of systematic error being double-counted, or do they mean something else? I see that Table 2 now introduces the SEVCO domains. It would be helpful if this classification system could be signposted earlier (e.g. at lines 132-133 where mapping is first mentioned). I was about to ask why the SEVCO system was chosen but then noticed this is explained at line 189. Perhaps the explanation could be moved up to the start of 2.1.3 so the rationale for using these criteria is clear before they are introduced?	<p>Thank you for pointing out this need for clarification. The following has now been included in the introduction:</p> <p>“To provide an organisational structure of the item bank, bias domains were used as a conceptual framework. Bias domains are themes such as e.g. study performance, analysis, and reporting, under which bias items can be organised/grouped.”</p> <p>We agree that the explanation for using the SEVCO system should be moved up. This has been done, and the revised text is as follows:</p> <p>“2.1.3 Mapping items onto bias domains</p> <p>Items were mapped onto single, best-fitting bias domains by one investigator (PW), with another (GEV) checking for agreement. Potential disagreements were resolved by discussion. The bias domains and definitions were taken from the Scientific Evidence Code System (SEVCO) research methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021b; FEVIR Platform Version 0.80.0, 06.12.2022). The list of domains and their definitions and identifiers are shown in Table 2. The SEVCO domains were chosen because of the grounding and consensus process used for developing their definitions (Alper et al., 2021a), making them in our opinion the most comprehensive and robust available to us at the time of the conduct of our work.”</p>
28	22. Lines 185-187: The statement here seems illogical. If a bias is not a “true” bias then why is it included? If threats to internal validity can’t be mapped to existing “domains” doesn’t that signal a need to revise the classification (e.g. add further “domains”) - and wouldn’t this project be the appropriate place to do so?	Thank you for this comment. We have included issues and discussion points that the experts participating in the focus group discussions emphasized as important when discussing internal validity of in vitro studies, we chose to include them for further discussion during further development of the INVITES-IN tool.

29	23. Line 189: Did the “grounding and consensus process” link to causality theory? If not, why not?	Thank you for this comment. The SEVCO terminology has been derived as described in Alper et al. 2021 . The process followed a 13-step Code System Development Protocol, involved more than 50 experts from more than 20 countries in a working group, and were based on 23 commonly used tool. We consider this to be a robust grounding and consensus process.
30	24. Table 2: “Choice of question bias” seems to be an aspect of external validity, not internal validity. Bias arising from setting the wrong question is independent of bias in outcomes due to research study design.	Thank you for this comment. We agree that “Choice of question bias” includes an aspect of external validity. However, we consider that it may also be an aspect of internal validity if e.g. the question leads to an incomplete testing of the hypothesis or selective harvesting of components of exposure. This is the reason for including this as a bias domain.
31	25. Table 2: “Conflicted interests bias” is a broad category that might not necessarily be independent of internal validity domains already being assessed. That’s because if investigators have conflicts that influence the study design and conduct this would be reflected in selection bias, attrition bias, detection bias etc.	We agree that “Conflicted interests bias” is a broad category that might not necessarily be independent of internal validity domains already being assessed. However, since the experts participating in the focus group discussions emphasized the importance of different types of conflicted interests for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies, we chose to include this as a bias domain.
32	26. Table 2: How is “metabias” different to “conflicted interests bias”? Wouldn’t both of these influences on investigators be expected to manifest themselves through consequent biases, such as selection, attrition, detection biases, etc, so why is a new “domain” needed? I don’t find the term “general distorting influence” intuitive to understand and it seems rather broad and vague	Thank you for this comment. We have clarified in the text: “We added two domains to support classification and analysis (“Metabias” and “Other”) to capture items that did not fit under the other bias domains (“metabias” was used for items that appear to affect multiple bias domains; “other” was for items that did not appear to relate to any bias domain).”
33	27. Table 2: What is the purpose of the “identifier” column in the table – the codes seem esoteric. Who are these intended for and how should they be interpreted?	Thank you for this comment. Table 2 has been deleted, as we realized that the important results as included in figure 2, and that all other information are included in supplemental materials 5.
34	28. Line 207: What is a “reasonable” demographic and regional distribution? (national, international, global?). Three groups of 6-8 participants limits how representative the study population can be, so maybe capturing expertise is more important than achieving demographic representativeness?	By “reasonable” demographic and regional distribution, we mean that we aim to include persons from different countries, ages, and genders.

35	29. Line 220: “Most had extensive experience” implies that some did not. Does this matter? Should participants also have had familiarity with the concept of systematic error, and if not was this explained to them?	<p>Participants reported level of experience as follows: No experience, 1-3 years of experience, 4-6 years of experience, more than 6 years of experience. Of the 20 participants in the focus group study, 17 reported more than 6 years of experience with in vitro studies, and 15 reported more than 6 years of experience with chemical risk assessment. This sentence is included to give the reader an impression of the participant group. All details are included in supplemental materials 2.</p> <p>The concepts of systematic error were explained to the participants in the invitation letter and at the beginning of the focus group discussion meetings.</p>
36	30. Lines 286-288: There is an implicit structure here, in that “items” are collected within “domains”. It would be helpful if both “items” and “domains” could be defined earlier in the manuscript.	<p>We agree that this needs to be included. These definitions are now included in the introduction and in the definition/glossary section.</p> <p>“Items are linguistically minimalist expressions of study assessment concepts. In the present study, “items” are derived by a normalisation process from study assessment criteria presented in study appraisal tools and described in focus group discussions, that potentially relate to the internal validity of an in vitro study.</p> <p>Bias domains are a conceptual framework for organising the limitations in conduct, design, or reporting of a study that have affected the internal validity of a study. Bias domains in the present study include but are not limited to detection, performance, and selection bias.”</p>
37	31. Table 3: I have no idea what this table is showing. The numbers are largely meaningless to me. Is this table necessary? If so, it needs clearer explanation.	We agree that that table is not necessary and have deleted the table.
38	32. Table 4: I don’t really understand this table. The caption says “bias” but hardly any of the statements in the table relate to bias. I also don’t understand the normalisation process, since the “raw” criteria appear more informative and intuitive than the “normalised” criteria.	Thank you for this comment. We agree that this table is not easy to understand. We have deleted this table, as all information is included in supplemental materials 5 (sheet 4), and we believe that the structure of the information is easier to understand in this sheet.

39	<p>33. Table 4: The statement that items 75 and 77 are “duplicates” only applies to the items after normalisation (the raw criteria clearly are not duplicates, which made me misunderstand what is a “duplicate” at first). Conversely, duplicate raw criteria (items 23 and 24) were separated out to different normalised criteria. (NB the text for the raw criterion of item 77 is missing one or two words so does not quite make sense)</p>	<p>This table has been deleted.</p>
40	<p>34. Lines 317-319: Perhaps the reason that “choice of question bias” only came from focus group discussions and not the literature is that this reflects external validity, not internal validity, so might have been phrased in different ways in the literature?</p>	<p>We agree that “Choice of question bias” includes an aspect of external validity. However, we consider that it may also be an aspect of internal validity if e.g. the question leads to an incomplete testing of the hypothesis or selective harvesting of components of exposure. This is the reason for including this as a bias domain.</p>
41	<p>35. Lines 321-323: If an investigator is perceived to have conflicts this might not necessarily lead to bias, but if it does lead to bias this would be reflected already in the “standard” types of bias assessed (selection, performance, attrition, detection, etc). Scientific studies can take steps to mitigate against biases and if these steps are successfully implemented then in theory investigators with conflicts would not introduce bias. Blinding/masking is an example of this. If all industry-sponsored trials were to be graded as having high risk of bias due to the perceived Col that would mean most clinical studies are biased. Yet in systematic reviews, and technology appraisals conducted by independent academic evidence synthesis groups, industry-sponsored trials are often classified as having low overall risk of bias. Taken to the level of implicit bias, a trait of all human beings, an argument could be made that no research can be free from Col. So, I think a category for bias due to conflicts would be inappropriate and unhelpful.</p>	<p>We agree that “Conflicted interests bias” is a broad category that might not necessarily be independent of internal validity domains already being assessed. However, systematic reviews comparing results from industry-sponsored trials with non-industry-sponsored trial have reported systematic differences, we cannot exclude the possibility of there being other factors at work. Additionally, since the experts participating in the focus group discussions emphasized the importance of different types of conflicted interests for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies, we chose to include this as a bias domain.</p>
42	<p>36. Lines 325-328: I find it surprising that the vague concept “blinding of operator” has been retained as an “other” type of bias (aka metabias). In a research study there are different groups of personnel who should be blinded/masked. Each group should be considered separately. I would expect the “blinding of operator”</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. We agree that there are different groups of personnel who should be blinded/masked, and that each group should be considered separately. However, as explained in the method section, we have aimed to preserve all conceptual differences, and to avoid making unwarranted assumptions in the data</p>

	term to be either (i) decomposed into the relevant personnel groups that it should cover (during the “normalisation” process), or (ii) be dropped from further consideration on account of being unhelpfully vague.	set as to what concepts the tool creators intended to represent by the words they were using.
43	37. Line 325: “Metabias” seems to me to just be a name for “other bias”. And confusingly it’s used in addition to “other bias” (what’s the difference?). The name “metabias” conveys an impression that there is a specific type of high-level bias being described here which is not the case. Why not just be directly clear about this and say “other bias” or “potential bias of uncertain significance” – terms that most people would find intuitive?	Thank you for this comment. We have clarified in the text: “We added two domains to support classification and analysis (“Metabias” and “Other”) to capture items that did not fit under the other bias domains (“metabias” was used for items that appear to affect multiple bias domains; “other” was for items that did not appear to relate to any bias domain).”
44	38. Lines 333-336: This explanation of deduplication is not easy to follow. Could it be expressed in a clearer way? I’m not sure about the EBTJ style requirement here but I think the information about deduplication should not be placed in the Figure caption here – could it go in the text or be embedded in small font at the bottom of the chart (below the x-axis)?	Thank you for this comment. The deduplication was performed using the Microsoft Excel deduplication feature, and in the final, deduplicated item bank, all duplicate items have been removed. The figure caption has been rewritten: “Note that the total count of items from all sources (column: ALL SOURCES) is lower than the sum of items from individual sources (columns: Cooper, IRIS, etc.) because some items appear in more than one source and are deduplicated in the final count.”
45	39. Supplementary material 5: This Excel file presents extensive data with no guidance on interpretation. I don’t know what to do with the information presented. The file is labelled “Item bank” but which part of the information presented is the item bank that is intended for readers to use?	We agree that a guidance to this excel file is needed. This is now included in supplemental material 5. The guidance includes the following information: A new sheet is included in supplemental materials 5 with information about each sheet in this excel file, and how the item bank may be useful to other researchers: “Sheet 0 “Information”. The information sheet that provides guidance on the contents of the item bank file. Sheet 1 “Item Bank”. The item bank, consisting of the reference numbers, unique items (n=405), and the bias domains under which each item has been categorized. Each item has a unique reference

		<p>number to facilitate identification and tracking through the analysis process.</p> <p>Sheet 2 “Items by Source”. The item bank, including the source and original criterion or discussion point from which each item was derived. Because some items appear in multiple sources, the total number of records in this sheet (n=497) is higher than the total number of items (n=405).</p> <p>Sheet 3 “Abstracted Criteria”. The full list of criteria and discussion points abstracted from the literature sources and focus group discussions, that were interpreted into the items.</p> <p>Sheet 4 “Included Criteria”. The criteria and discussion points containing concepts that ended up being interpreted into items and included in the item bank. This sheet shows how the criteria and discussion points were interpreted into items by the investigators.</p> <p>Sheet 5 “Excluded Criteria”. The criteria and discussion points that were not interpreted into items in the item bank.</p> <p>Sheet 6 “Lookups”. The source for the drop-down lists of bias items, designed to reduce data input errors when creating the item bank.</p> <p>Sheet 1 and 2 have been set up with filters to assist with exploring the item bank, allowing e.g. only items associated with analysis bias to be displayed (sheet 1), or only items associated with a specific source (sheet 2). The sheets are locked but not password protected to prevent accidental editing. To filter the data in the sheets, the user should right-click the tab for the sheet they are interested in filtering and select “Pause Protection”.</p>
46	40. Supplementary material 5: Why does “incomplete data on confounding variables” map to “attrition bias”? In my	Thank you for this comment. We interpret incomplete data as absence of data.

	understanding, incomplete information on the confounders could be a source of uncertainty, but not necessarily a source of systematic error.	
47	41. Supplementary material 5: Some of the phrases are insufficiently clear. For example, I don't know what "use of atlas for image bank analysis" means or why it might be related to systematic error.	Thank you for this comment. We have included issues and discussion points that the experts participating in the focus group discussions emphasized as important when discussing internal validity of in vitro studies, we have included them for further discussion during further development of the INVITES-IN tool.
48	42. Supplementary material 5: I found the wording of some of the normalised criteria difficult to understand and the technical presentation style appears to be inconsistent. Some criteria are neutral phrases which give no interpretation in relation to systematic error (e.g. "description of dropouts", "sources of funding") whilst others imply (mitigation of) systematic error (e.g. "control of confounders", "incomplete test of the hypothesis"). I am not sure how readers are intended to interpret or use these normalised criteria.	<p>Thank you for this comment. We have clarified in the discussion:</p> <p>“4.1 Normalisation and exclusion decisions</p> <p>Our process for analysing criteria from literature sources and discussion points from the focus group discussions into normalised items was naturally subjective and completed in finite time. We expect that additional rounds of analysis would have eliminated further trivial differences between items and reduced the number of items overall (items 202 “exposure misclassification” and 208 “misclassification of exposure” are a particularly obvious example of where we missed conceptual duplicates). Other researchers could reasonably argue that differences between items such as 105 “storage of test compound” and 2097 “storage of test materials” are functionally equivalent and that preserving the difference unhelpfully inflates the number of items in the item bank.”</p> <p>Our counterargument to this point is we felt that preserving even small conceptual differences might be significant to the development of an INVITES-IN appraisal tool in a way we cannot anticipate during the item identification process. We felt that if we normalised away subtle differences, we risked losing important nuance and context that we would not be able to retrieve later. This could have a particular impact on the more detailed prompts, elicitation questions, and guidance that will form part of the eventual INVITES-IN tool. We therefore normalised items in such a way as to preserve detail, and it is in the post-Delphi stage of INVITES-IN (when we create the beta version of our tool) that we will remove detail in the items that is not helpful for our context.</p>

		<p>Our exclusion decisions were similarly subjective. Other researchers may not agree with them, and it is possible we excluded concepts that should have been part of our final item bank. A limitation of our method is that we did not document all reasons for our exclusions (see Supplemental Materials 6, sheet 5) as it was too time-intensive to give informative reasons for hundreds of exclusion decisions based on sometimes lengthy discussion. In general, we would note that using a larger team of researchers to make exclusion and normalization decisions, and conducting more rounds of normalization, would lead to improved results. However, with hundreds of items and each round taking many person hours (we estimate two people need 20 hours of discussion for 400 items), a decision must be made as to the cost-benefit trade-off of running each round of analysis.</p> <p>To compensate for limitations and potential differences of opinion around our approach and resulting items, we have included in our item bank all the uninterpreted source criteria and discussion points, to give other teams all the materials they need to reinterpret our data. It should also be noted that this study was a discovery exercise with the sole aim of collecting items for the creation of our item bank. Any reinterpretation of original tools and criteria for our specific purposes should not be interpreted as critique of those tools: it is a linguistic process of simplification that removes detail and information about context, to make it easier to identify and analyse as many as possible of the core internal validity concepts being expressed by the tools in aggregate.</p>
<p>“Are the additional post-hoc or exploratory analyses (if any) added by the authors justified, methodologically sound, and informative?”</p>		
	<p>No comments.</p>	
<p>“Are the authors’ findings, based on the planned and unplanned analyses, justified?”</p>		
<p>49</p>	<p>The main comment here is about the ease of interpretation of the large amount of supplementary data provided, as well as a discussion of its potential utility for the wide scientific community, beyond the development of INVITES-IN. This could be addressed by drafting an accompanying document guiding the reader through the collated data. Here reiteration of how this step of the project fits into the development of the tool may improve clarity for the reader.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. A guidance to supplemental 5, the excel file containing the item bank and all data created in the process of preparing the item bank, has now been included in this file. We believe that no instructions/additional information are needed for the other supplemental files which includes the participant invitation letter, the participant characteristics, the slides that were presented in</p>

		the focus group discussion meetings, the anonymized transcripts from the focus group discussion meetings, and the code for Figure 2,
50	43. The manuscript does not clearly explain who the intended users of the item bank are (if wider than those developing the INVITES-IN tool) or how the information should be used. I presume that the final item bank is in the Excel file in supplementary material 5, but this is not clearly signposted to the reader, and does not contain any guidance or instructions on how to interpret the extensive information presented, some of which I don't understand (see my specific comments below). As such, it feels like the manuscript currently stops short of providing a complete and useful output.	<p>Thank you for pointing out this need for clarification. In addition to being the data set used as a starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN, the item bank is intended to be functioning as an extendable database providing a common resource from which specific tools can be derived. We present the method for the preparation of the item bank and the item bank is this manuscript, so that other researchers may use the item bank or adapt our method for developing validity assessment tools with other goals. This is now described in the introduction.</p> <p>A guidance to supplemental 5, the excel file containing the item bank and all data created in the process of preparing the item bank, has now been included in this file.</p>
51	44. Lines 338-339: Identifying items that “may be relevant” feels like a weak outcome from this extensive systematic process. Aren't these items definitely relevant? Isn't the purpose of an item bank to provide relevant items? It may be that relevance is yet to be finalised because this is ongoing work – however, that isn't explained to the reader until they read on...	<p>Thank you for this question. As some of the bias items have been derived from validity assessment tools for human and experimental animal studies, it could be that not all items in the bank are relevant for in vitro studies. This is the reason for using the phrase “may be relevant”.</p> <p>The next step is to identify the items in the item bank that are of importance for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies, which will be a separate study described in another manuscript.</p>
52	45. Lines 347-351: Having read through the manuscript the reader is informed at this point that the work is ongoing and that more phases are underway. I am therefore unclear what readers are expected to do with the information in supplementary material 5, which I assume is incomplete, and I find it difficult to understand why the unit of information presented in the manuscript is considered useful.	<p>Thank you for sharing these reflections. In a systematic review of quality assessment tools for in vitro studies (Tran et al., 2021), the conclusion was that none of the existing tools cover all critical aspects for systematic review of in vitro studies. We aim to address this in the creation of INVITES-IN by using a comprehensive overview of items identified as having the potential to introduce bias to in vitro studies as the starting point for the creation of the tool.</p> <p>In addition to being the data set used as a starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN, the item bank is intended to be functioning as an extendable database providing a common resource from which</p>

		<p>specific tools can be derived. We present the method for the preparation of the item bank and the item bank is this manuscript, so that other researchers may use the item bank or adapt our method for developing validity assessment tools with other goals. This is now described in the introduction. We consider that transparency of the process is critical, to make it possible for other researchers to know exactly what we have done. Therefore, all data created throughout the preparation of the item bank is included in the supplemental materials.</p> <p>We have attempted to clarify why we consider the unit of information presented in the manuscript useful through revisions of the introduction and the discussion.</p>
53	<p>46. Lines 351-352: The Discussion says that a risk of bias tool will be created from the reported work with a manageable number of signalling questions but there is no indication of how this will be done. It feels unsatisfactory that the reader is left in limbo with a half-finished item bank and no clear indication of what happens next.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. We would like to point out that the item bank created in the present study is the finalized data set that will be used as the starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN. However, given that assessment of in vitro studies is likely to become a fast-moving field, we acknowledge that there may be a need for the item bank to be extended.</p> <p>We agree that more information about what will happen next should be included, and have therefore included the following text in the introduction:</p> <p>“The creation of INVITES-IN consists of four methodological stages, that we refer to as “studies”:</p> <p>Study 1. Creating a comprehensive database of issues that may affect the internal validity of in vitro studies of any design.</p> <p>Study 2. Prioritising issues from the database according to their relevance to the assessment of internal validity of eukaryotic cell culture systems.</p> <p>Study 3. Creating a beta version of an appraisal tool based on analysis of the prioritised issues identified in stage 2.</p>

		<p>Study 4. Creating a final release version of the tool, based on user-testing of the beta version.</p> <p>Due to the complexity of the INVITES-IN project, we are publishing our methods and results in three manuscripts. The present manuscript describes the methods and results for Study 1. A second manuscript will describe Study 2. The third manuscript will describe Studies 3 and 4. The planned methods for all four INVITES-IN studies, the creation and user testing of INVITES-IN are described in two protocols (Mathisen et al., 2023; Svendsen et al., 2023).”</p>
54	<p>47. Lines 368-377: It’s difficult for the reader to visualise the relevance of this information, because only part of the project is presented in this manuscript. The discourse here seems to be picking apart small issues that are difficult to relate to any overall wider context.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing out this need for clarification. We have simplified and explained in the discussion:</p> <p>“4.1 Normalisation and exclusion decisions</p> <p>Our process for analysing criteria from literature sources and discussion points from the focus group discussions into normalised items was naturally subjective and completed in finite time. We expect that additional rounds of analysis would have eliminated further trivial differences between items and reduced the number of items overall (items 202 “exposure misclassification” and 208 “misclassification of exposure” are a particularly obvious example of where we missed conceptual duplicates). Other researchers could reasonably argue that differences between items such as 105 “storage of test compound” and 2097 “storage of test materials” are functionally equivalent and that preserving the difference unhelpfully inflates the number of items in the item bank.</p> <p>Our counterargument to this point is we felt that preserving even small conceptual differences might be significant to the development of an INVITES-IN appraisal tool in a way we cannot anticipate during the item identification process. We felt that if we normalised away subtle differences, we risked losing important nuance and context that we would not be able to retrieve later. This could have a particular impact on the more detailed prompts, elicitation questions, and guidance that will form part of the eventual INVITES-IN tool. We therefore normalised items in such a way as to preserve detail, and it is in the post-Delphi stage of INVITES-IN (when we create the beta version of our tool) that we will remove detail in the items that is not helpful for our context.”</p>

55	48. Lines 427-429: “Domains that would have been almost empty” – this needs explanation. It’s not clear which or how many items a “domain” can contain and hence unclear whether a domain with few, or many, items would be a good or bad thing.	<p>Thank you for pointing out this need for explanation. We have rewritten and explained in the result section:</p> <p>“Items relating to confounding covariate bias (n=7) were contributed by tools designed for assessing the internal validity of epidemiological studies. These were considered by the focus groups as potentially important for assessing the internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> studies that use primary biological samples; however, as this type of study is outside the scope of INVITES-IN at this time, this issue was not discussed in detail and the focus groups added no further items for this domain. Only three items relating to conflicted interest bias were derived from the literature sources. The focus group discussions contributed six items, to give eight items in total under this domain after removal of duplicates. Conflicted interest bias was considered important by the focus groups, with several examples presented of where participants were concerned that this had impacted studies; however, the groups found it challenging to identify specific criteria for how conflict of interest could be assessed independently of the impact it has on decisions about how to design, conduct, or report a study.”</p>
56	49. Line 430: What purpose? What evidence is there for this statement? No testing or attempted use of the item bank list appears to have been conducted.	<p>Thank you for these questions. The purpose of the item bank is to be of utility for tool development exercises such as creation of INVITES-IN, and to provide a robust methodology for grounding tool development in the existing literature and expertise. This information is now included in the introduction.</p> <p>Overall, we believe the item bank fulfills its purpose and will be a valuable dataset of potential bias concepts that can support the development of tools for the assessment of <i>in vitro</i> studies in the field of toxicology.</p>
57	50. Line 434: It’s very difficult for the reader to understand what use these 405 items are, without tangible examples of how they could be applied or worked into a risk of bias tool. This manuscript feels like it is only describing a data collection exercise and missing the analysis and application.	<p>It is a data collection exercise, and we are presenting a dataset and the method for creating it. Analysis and use of the dataset for our specific purpose is coming in the following manuscripts (a Delphi process to determine of all the items that may be useful, which ones are in fact useful; and a tool development and presentation manuscript where the items are interpreted into an appraisal tool).</p>

		Each manuscript is lengthy and complex and therefore worth presenting separately – the alternative being one 20k word manuscript which is far too complex for peer-review or omits a lot of detail important for understanding and replicating processes (should the community be interested in this). We may write a commentary once the project is finished, providing an overview and key lessons from the whole project.
“Other comments”		
58	51. Line 86: “systematic error or bias” - aren’t these the same thing? Perhaps reword to “systematic error, i.e. bias”? (if these terms are not considered synonymous then definitions would be helpful).	The introduction has been revised. Bias is defined in the glossary: “Bias is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual studies or across studies, and may be introduced through limitations in the design, conduct, or reporting of a study.”
59	52. Line 88: “potential for systematic error or risk of bias” – perhaps reword to avoid this being misread as “potential for risk of bias”.	The introduction has been revised. Bias is defined in the glossary: “Bias is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual studies or across studies, and may be introduced through limitations in the design, conduct, or reporting of a study.”
60	53. Figure 1: The transcript from the focus group presented here is in abbreviated note form and doesn’t make sense without additional context. A clearer example, or an explanation of what the focus group respondent is referring to, would be helpful.	As described in the protocol, participants have been anonymized, the transcripts have been machine generated, and only errors in transcription affecting coding and interpretation of the discussion have been corrected.
61	54. Line 199 and elsewhere: In the interests of clear communication can plain English be used instead of acronyms where possible? For instance, “FGD” could be largely replaced with “focus group(s)” – the “D” part isn’t really necessary in all cases is it?	We have replaced unnecessary abbreviations with the full names to increase the readability.
62	55. Line 205: An example of a difficult-to-read sentence that would be nicer in plain English.	We have replaced unnecessary abbreviations with the full names to increase the readability.
63	56. Lines 215-217: This repeats the statement in the preceding paragraph.	Thank you for pointing out this. We have deleted this sentence.
64	57. Lines 303-309: Table 3 caption. Also applies to Table 4 caption: I am not sure about the EBTJ style requirement here but I think the information indicated by asterisks would be better placed as table footnotes. The current caption occupies a whole paragraph, and the	Table 3 has been deleted from the revised manuscript.

	reader has no idea what to do with the asterisk-marked information at this point as they haven't reached the table itself.	
65	58. Lines 355-357: It's not clear where this paragraph is leading. How would this information influence future development of assessment tools?	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. The manuscript has been rewritten and improved:</p> <p>“Firstly, there is a tendency for tools to collapse multiple points of evaluation into a single criterion, in a way that may be problematic. For example, the uninterpreted criterion number 126 (see Supplemental Materials 5, sheet 2 – reference numbers are in column B) states: “Was the exposure period, timing (i.e., cell passage number, insufficient culture maturity for the adequate expression of mature cell markers; insufficient treatment or measurement duration for the production of protein above the level of detection), frequency, and duration of exposure sensitive for the assay/model system of interest, particularly in the absence of a positive control?”. This combines multiple aspects of exposure and use of positive controls, into a single prompt. The uninterpreted criterion number 130, from the same tool, states: “Are there concerns regarding the need for positive controls (e.g., concerns that the effects of interest may be inhibited or otherwise poorly manifest in the test system, for example due to differences from in vivo biology)? If used, was the selected positive test substance (and dose) reasonable and appropriate and was the intended positive response induced?” This criterion covers several additional aspects of the use of positive controls, relating to the ability of a test system to manifest an outcome of interest.”</p>
66	59. Line 378: This paragraph starts “secondly” but I have already read two preceding paragraphs thinking they were the first two issues. The structure and signposting of the Discussion could be improved.	<p>Thank you for informing us about the need for structuring of the discussion. We have rearranged the discussion, included subheadings for the different parts of the discussion, and rewritten the text in a part of the discussion. We hope this have increased the clarity.</p>
67	60. Lines 378-380: I don't understand this – what does “map naturally onto” mean here?	<p>Thank you for pointing out the need for explanation. The rewritten manuscript now explains in the methods:</p> <p>“2.2.1. Domain mapping Each item was categorised according to the single best-fitting bias domain relating to the item.”</p>
68	61. Lines 378-392: This paragraph is difficult to follow, as the “examples” are just lists of code numbers. I don't understand this text which seems very verbose and struggles to get to the point.	<p>Thank you for pointing out this. The numbers have now been replaced with the description of the item.</p>

69	62. Supplementary material 1 states that an inclusion criterion for the focus groups was “Active in the field of in vitro research in academia, governmental institution (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or private research institution”. However, supplementary material 2 states that one person had “No experience” with invitro studies. Why was the person who did not meet the eligibility criteria included?	The following explanation has now been included in supplemental materials 2: “One person didn't have hands on experience doing <i>in vitro</i> research and reported 0 years of experience. However, this person is, and have been, involved in much relevant work on <i>in vitro</i> studies such as e.g. development of adverse outcome pathways, so we still found that this person had valuable <i>in vitro</i> expertise.”
70	63. Supplementary material 4: Has the correct file been uploaded? Large parts of the focus group transcript are nonsensical.	This is the correct file containing the raw data from the focus group meeting discussions. As described in the protocol, participants have been anonymized, the transcripts have been machine generated, and only errors in transcription affecting coding and interpretation of the discussion have been corrected.